

Enabling Open Science Through Research Code

Episode 3: Opening Up Research Code

Session information

Webpage	https://rsse.africa/events-rsse-africa/2024-12-12/
Date	12 December 2024
Time	08:30 - 10:00 am UTC (your time zone)
Facilitators	Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal Anelda van der Walt
Co-facilitators	Jyoti Bhogal Mireille Grobbelaar
Speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adeyinka Oresanya, Software Developer, Community Health Analytics in Open Source Software (CHAOSS) ● Chioma Onyido, Bioinformatics Engineer, Bioconductor & Covenant University ● Juan Pablo Flores, Senior Program Manager, GitHub ● Kate Huddleston, Senior Lecturer, Department of General Linguistics, Stellenbosch University, South Africa ● Mars Lee, Technical Illustrator, NumPy & Open Source Design
Zoom registration	https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZErcOqsrDssHNV-TY6OG89MZkwOtXs-oNF_

Schedule

Time	Activity	Speakers
8:30 UTC	Giving everyone time to join	Facilitator: Anelda
8:35 UTC	Welcome	Facilitator: Anelda
8:40 UTC	Introduction to opening up research code	Facilitator: Saranjeet
8:50 UTC	Introducing our speakers <i>Tell us a bit about your background and your current role?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What did you study and where? ○ Do you have postgrad qualifications? In what area? ○ What is the title of your current role? ○ Give a one-sentence summary of what you do in this role 	Facilitator: Anelda Adeyinka Oresanya Chioma Onyido Juan Pablo Flores Kate Huddleston Mars Lee
9:10 UTC	Polls	Facilitator: Saranjeet
9:15 UTC	Panel discussion 1. What does it mean to make research code open, and what do you think are the benefits? 2. How has using open-source tools helped you in your research?	Facilitator: Anelda 1. Adeyinka Oresanya Juan Pablo Flores Mars Lee 2. Chioma Onyido Kate Huddleston Facilitator: Jyoti
9:25 UTC	3. What are the biggest challenges you've faced in sharing code openly, and how did you	3. Adeyinka Oresanya Chioma Onyido

Time	Activity	Speakers
9:35 UTC	<p>overcome them? What practices do you follow to cite other's code? How can others cite your code?</p> <p>4. How do you balance the need for open access with concerns about intellectual property and data privacy? How would you identify if an open-source code is reusable?</p> <p>5. What advice do you have for audience members who want to learn about skills and tools to help them open up their research code? Which communities can they join? What open learning resources can they refer to?</p>	<p>4. Juan Pablo Flores Mars Lee</p> <p>Facilitator: Anelda</p> <p>5. Adeyinka Oresanya Chioma Onyido Juan Pablo Flores Kate Huddleston Mars Lee</p>
9:45 UTC	Q&A	Facilitator: Jyoti
9:55 UTC	Wrap up and next steps	Facilitator: Anelda

Resources and info from partners

RSSE Africa

- Website: <https://rsse.africa>
- Sign up for our newsletter:
<https://talarify.us14.list-manage.com/subscribe?u=35d5db26d3b108b9ef9b9ac43&id=55e9f5a692>
- Join our LinkedIn group, where you can also share information with the broader community: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12903402/>

RSE Asia

- Website: https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/
- For the latest news, events, activities, and opportunities, follow us on our [LinkedIn page](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rse-asia-association/) (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/rse-asia-association/>)
- To join the RSE Asia community, please fill out our short [Community Membership Form](https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1XSxDaTJzcNyGeDYXyJNVg1TDCo7un18PLFNiK6_jL2q/edit) (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1XSxDaTJzcNyGeDYXyJNVg1TDCo7un18PLFNiK6_jL2q/edit)

AREN

- Website: <https://africanrn.org/>
- Sign up: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeeFkD5A4D9l6ncQWjKBil-GqBOzL-JMe7Fx3ijUYEjHjDUoQ/viewform>

ReSA

- Website: <https://www.researchsoft.org/>
- Sign up for the newsletter: <https://www.researchsoft.org/news/>
- The [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#)
 - Become a signatory: <https://adore.software/sign/>

Questions for organisers, facilitators and/or speakers

- What are the best practices for ensuring confidentiality when making research data open, especially in situations where grouping by demographics and unique circumstances is critical? I recently came across a suggestion to use data swapping, but it seems unsuitable for such cases.
 - The saying - as open as possible, as closed as necessary applies. Not all data should be openly available. Sometimes, it's not possible to share anonymised/de-identified data
 - In these cases, it is okay to share only the metadata - the data that describes the actual data. It still allows others to understand what data was used in the study and they could contact the PI or researchers on the study to explore collaboration etc
 - It will also depend on the consent form of the data participants - what they agreed to in terms of how the data could be used inside and beyond the specific study
- @Juan Pablo Flores - how different is Codespaces from say VS Code?
 - you can run VS Code within Codespaces. Codespaces setup a whole environment for you.

Shared resources from the session

- From Mars:
 - examples of my open research 'code'- or rather sharing my process and resources as a technical illustrator:
 - My repository, with my art source files, sketches, comic script and brainstorming artifacts from brainstorming with the NumPy community:
<https://github.com/MarsBarLee/gcod-numpy-2023>
 - My talk at PyData NYC being the only artist/under-represented population in open source: https://youtu.be/Gv_Ea94wquM?si=a4llxR0pEMxsvn_Z&t=43
 - Blog post on timeline:
<https://medium.com/@marsbarlee/gcod-numpy-contributor-comics-project-roadmap-521280503fbd>
- From Debs:
 - Thanks, Anelda..for the chance to brag about the beauty of open science. 😊

- 🖱️ We're looking for contributors to help us develop a "Research 101" course, to address the diversity gap in the research landscape:
- <https://github.com/npdebs/Pre-seeds-Program/>
- If you can contribute your time, expertise, and/or knowledge, please reach out to debs@we-are-ols.org, or connect with Debs on LinkedIn:
- [linkedin.com/in/deborah-udoh-b0a720188/](https://www.linkedin.com/in/deborah-udoh-b0a720188/)
- From, Mars:
 - Krita, open source illustration software (break free from Adobe!):
<https://krita.org/en/>
 - My Krita source file for page 1 of my NumPy comics:
<https://github.com/MarsBarLee/gsod-numpy-2023/blob/main/source-files/pg1.kra>
 - https://docs.dyspatch.io/localization/uploading_localizations/
- **GitHub** (<https://github.com>) – A web-based platform for version control and collaborative software development using Git.
- **How to Contribute to NumPy comic** (<https://heyzine.com/flip-book/3e66a13901.html>) – An interactive flipbook-style comic guide explaining how to contribute to the NumPy open-source project.
- **ORCID and GitHub Memorandum of Understanding** (<https://info.orcid.org/orcid-and-github-sign-memorandum-of-understanding/>) – Announcement of ORCID and GitHub's agreement to enhance researcher authentication and visibility.
- **Nature Article on Dataset Sharing** (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01710-x>) – A scientific paper discussing best practices for sharing datasets in research.
- **GitHub Citation Files** (<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/managing-your-repositorys-settings-and-features/customizing-your-repository/about-citation-files>) – Documentation on adding citation files to GitHub repositories for proper attribution of code and projects.
- **GitHub Repository Topics** (<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/managing-your-repositorys-settings-and-features/customizing-your-repository/classifying-your-repository-with-topics>) – Guide on using topics to categorize and improve discoverability of repositories.
- **Choose a License** (<https://choosealicense.com/>) – A resource to help developers select an open-source license for their projects.

- **GitHub Repository Licensing**
(<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/managing-your-repositorys-settings-and-features/customizing-your-repository/licensing-a-repository>) – Instructions on how to add a license to a GitHub repository.
- **NASA Open Science (TOPS)** (<https://science.nasa.gov/open-science/tops/>) – NASA’s initiative to promote transparency, openness, and inclusivity in scientific research.
- **Don't Use This Code** (<https://www.dontusethecode.com>) – A humorous website highlighting bad coding practices and anti-patterns.
- **Bioconductor** (<https://www.bioconductor.org/>) – A repository of open-source software for bioinformatics and computational biology.
 - The mission of the Bioconductor project is to develop, support, and disseminate free, open-source software that facilitates rigorous and reproducible data analysis from current and emerging biological assays. We are dedicated to building a diverse, collaborative, and welcoming community of developers and data scientists
 - Bioconductor has a vast community that helps troubleshoot your errors.
- **Why Use BiocManager for Installation**
(<https://bioconductor.org/install/index.html#why-biocmanagerinstall>) – Explanation of why BiocManager is the preferred method for installing Bioconductor packages in R.
- **CRAN (Comprehensive R Archive Network)** (<https://cran.r-project.org/>) – The official repository for R packages, documentation, and software distributions.
- **Open Science Framework (OSF)** (<https://osf.io/>) – A free, open-source platform to support open collaboration, research management, and data sharing.
- **CZI Essential Open Source Software (EOSS) Program**
(<https://chanzuckerberg.com/eoss/>) – A funding initiative by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative to support critical open-source software for scientific research.
- **GitHub Contribution Guidelines**
(<https://docs.github.com/en/communities/setting-up-your-project-for-healthy-contributions/setting-guidelines-for-repository-contributors>) – Guide on defining contribution guidelines to help maintain healthy and inclusive GitHub repositories.
- **Setting Up a GitHub Project for Healthy Contributions**
(<https://docs.github.com/en/communities/setting-up-your-project-for-healthy-contributions>) – Best practices for fostering an active and sustainable open-source project on GitHub.

- **Git and GitHub for Efficient Project Management** – A mini-blog post/tutorial on leveraging Git and GitHub for streamlined collaboration in research software projects.
- **Diátaxis Documentation Framework** – A structured approach to documentation that separates tutorials, how-to guides, explanations, and references for clarity and usability.
- **Session Info in R** – Using `sessionInfo()` in R to list all dependencies used in a session, with a similar approach available in the command line via `script filename.txt`.
- **GitHub Codespaces** – A cloud-based development environment that allows users to run, edit, and debug code directly from their browser with GitHub integration.
- **All Contributors** – A framework for recognizing all contributors to a project, not just those who write code, using a structured contribution model.
- **Outreachy** (<https://www.outreachy.org/>) – A paid internship program supporting diversity in open source and free software by providing remote work opportunities.
- **Bad Licenses Repository** (<https://github.com/ErikMcClure/bad-licenses>) – A GitHub repository highlighting problematic or unclear open-source licenses.
- **CHAOSS Community** (<https://chaoss.community/>) – An open-source initiative focused on measuring and improving the health of open-source communities.
- **Bioconductor Support Forum** (<https://support.bioconductor.org/>) – A community-driven Q&A site for troubleshooting and discussions related to Bioconductor packages and workflows.
- **Microbiome Virtual International Forum** (<https://www.microbiome-vif.org/en-US>) – A global platform promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange in microbiome research.
- **GitHub Education** (<https://github.com/education>) – Resources and programs for students, educators, and academic institutions using GitHub in education.
- **The Carpentries** (<https://carpentries.org/>) – A community-led organization providing training in foundational coding and data science skills for researchers.
- **Open Source Design** (<https://opensource.design.net/>) – A community and job board dedicated to connecting designers with open-source projects.
- **Nature Article on Open Science**
(<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-024-03344-y>) – A news article discussing recent developments and challenges in open science.